

Antecedents of Job Satisfaction among Engineering Faculty

Somasekhar Donthu*

Dr.Sathish Babu Adipudi**

Sripathi Kalvakolanu***

Abstract

The role of academic professionals is not much researched on the dimensions of professional satisfaction. Measuring job satisfaction needs to assess the extent to which the job holders favorably evaluate their feelings or cognitions about the job. With many institutes spreading the engineering education among the students, it is imperative that the quality and outcomes of these programmes are highly dependent on the faculty members who play key role in imparting this knowledge. In this context, the present study is taken up to understand the job satisfaction among the engineering faculty. An explorative study was conducted among 500 engineering faculty working in the engineering colleges in the Kadapa district of Andhra Pradesh, India. An effort is made to elicit opinions of faculty members about various factors such as salary, career development and working environment etc. The Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) was used to capture the facets of job satisfaction among the respondents. The study indicated that factors such as gender, designation, age, experience and the overall job satisfaction were independent of one another. However, factors such as compensation and working conditions were found to be related to the overall job satisfaction.

Key Words: Job Satisfaction; Demographics; Engineering Faculty; MSQ;

1 Introduction

An important yet undermined to be called a profession is 'academics'. In the field of higher education, the role of academic professionals is not much researched on the dimensions of professional satisfaction and the corresponding value proposition to the institute and society at large.

Job satisfaction can be understood as the extent to which an individual is content with her/his job. This comes from looking at the job both on an overall perspective as well as specific facets of jobs. Job satisfaction, as derived from the attitude model, essentially can have the cognitive, affective, and behavioral components. Thus, measuring job satisfaction needs to assess the extent to which the job holders favorably evaluate their feelings or cognitions about the job. Research in this domain shows that employees who show high satisfaction in their jobs tend to show higher productivity, involvement and low tendency to leave the job (Sowmya & Panchanatham, 2011).

Among the definitions of job satisfaction, that of Locke (1976) is the popular and widely accepted one. Locke defines job satisfaction as "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences".

* Doctoral Research Scholar, Department of Commerce and Business Administration, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur, Assistant Professor, Sri Venkateswara College of Engineering, Tirupati, INDIA

** Professor, P.G. Department of Commerce & Management Studies, V.R.S. & Y.R.N. (PG) College, Chirala, INDIA

*** Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies, Vignan's Foundation for Science, Technology, & Research (Deemed to be University), Guntur, INDIA

The profession of teaching is distinct from others, as it is rendered with service orientation. Professionals who take up this career render their services selflessly and without looking for the balancing benefits. However, it is important that these faculty fraternities are also happy and content with their jobs, which will make them go that extra mile in building a great nation. India has seen a big leap in the number of institutions offering engineering programmes in the past two decades. There are about 10,000 institutes offering the engineering programmes across the country. This number is significantly high in the southern states. Andhra Pradesh and Telangana constitute nearly 1500 institutes together. With these many institutes spreading the engineering education among the students, it is imperative that the quality and outcomes of these programmes are highly dependent on the faculty members who play key role in imparting this knowledge. In this context, the present study is taken up to understand the job satisfaction among the engineering faculty. The study mainly focuses on assessing the facets that affect job satisfaction, while also measuring the impact of those factors on job satisfaction.

2 Literature Review

Hagedorn (2000), in their work on studying job satisfaction related dimensions, developed a conceptual framework that identified two categories of variables labelled mediators and triggers. Each category comprises several individual and environmental characteristics. The mediator category components are seen to be having the features to predict the levels of satisfaction.

When coming to the teaching fraternity, globally they are coming together on shared platforms. Increased number of academic staff is spreading around the world and also there are faculty exchange programmes on rise. However, not all developing countries have caught this opportunity. Many of the developing countries are lagging in this context and are at the bottom level of unequal academic relationships (Altbach 2004).

Sabharwal and Corley (2009) studied and categorized the job satisfaction related variables into three categories. According to their classification satisfaction may be influenced by factors ranging from demographic, institutional as well as career related issues.

Balbachevsky and Schwartzman (2010) made attempt to study different factor in the academic context and how academic institutions put job satisfaction in place. Through their study they identified significant differences in terms of governance styles across the institutions (Balbachevsky and Schwartzman, 2010).

Jones and Weinrib (2010) studied the differences of conditions prevalent in the academic institutes. Their study concluded that among the individuals who opt for research and teaching professions, there are significant differences in conditions of employment and the pay they receive (Jones and Weinrib 2010).

While studying the factors that influence job satisfaction among the university professors, Metcalfe et al. (2011) found that the size of the institutions may also play role. Their study identified that the professors who belong to smaller universities were considering themselves more influential in decision making than those of a larger universities.

Nagar. K. (2012) studied the job satisfaction among 153 university teachers. The study focused on assessing how organizational commitment and satisfaction were related among the teachers when they undergo burnout. The study found females to be more satisfied with their jobs than their male counterparts. Also, the study identified that greater job satisfaction was leading to increased organizational commitment.

Tahir. S. & Sajid. S.M. (2014) made a comparative analysis of level of job satisfaction among teachers of a private management college in Delhi and a college of Delhi University. Their study used Paula Lester's Teacher Job Satisfaction questionnaire to collect the information pertaining to job satisfaction. The study found significant levels of differences in satisfaction among the male and female faculty members while no big differences were found between the two institutes compared.

Kumar et. al (2017) in their study on job satisfaction of teachers working in schools and colleges found nature of work as an important factor for determining the job satisfaction. They found differences in gender giving priority to factors of job satisfaction. While the male members were more inclined towards growth factor, the female were interested in the nature of work.

Chintala. G. & Rao. H. (2017) studied the job characteristics and the corresponding job satisfaction levels among the teachers working in technical institutions in Telangana state. From the review of literature, it is drawn that there is a greater need to study the specific nuances of the job satisfaction among the faculty of higher education institutions. There are very few studies in this area. The engineering faculty of the Andhra Pradesh state is under severe pressure to deliver best results, as the state places higher importance on transforming itself into an educational hub. In this context, a study on job satisfaction is taken up with the following methodology.

3 Methodology

The present study is formulated using an explorative research design. The study attempts to explore job satisfaction among engineering faculty members. Most studies that are taken up in measuring job satisfaction use a quantitative approach. Research in assessing job satisfaction has progressed by using validated instruments such as the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) (Weiss et al., 1967). Over the period of time, several new versions and types of satisfaction study questionnaires have evolved. MSQ is among the comprehensive forms of assessing job satisfaction levels. Holmberg (2017) is of the opinion that some studies have adapted qualitative methodology by preferring individual interviews (Holmberg et al., 2017). Hence in the present study the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire was used to interview the respondents.

The main data for the study is collected by conducting personal interviews with faculty members of engineering colleges, Heads of Departments, Principals and management in Kadapa district of Andhra Pradesh, India during 2016-17. An effort is made to elicit opinions of faculty members about various factors such as salary, career development and working environment etc. The Questionnaire (MSQ) was circulated to all the faculty members in the engineering colleges in Kadapa district. Purposive sampling technique was used to select engineering colleges. Simple Random Sampling Technique was used for selecting the faculty members. A total number of 500 faculty members were selected from different colleges for the present study. Engineering colleges in Kadapa district affiliated to JNTU, Anantapur and Yogi Vemana University having five years of standing were considered for inclusion in the study. Faculty members who came forward voluntarily to participate in the study were considered.

Secondary data from the records, articles and other documentary materials maintained by All India Council for Technical Education, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Books on technical education, News Papers etc. were included in the study.

3.1 Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are

- To identify the effect of demographic factors on the overall job satisfaction of the employees
- To study the relationship between the different job facets and job satisfaction

3.2 Hypotheses

The following null and supporting hypotheses are formulated to assess the study objectives.

H01: There is no significant relationship between gender and job satisfaction among faculty

H02: There is no significant relationship between designation and job satisfaction among faculty

H03: There is no significant relationship between working conditions and job satisfaction among faculty

H04: There is no significant relationship between compensation and job satisfaction among faculty

4 Minnesota Job Satisfaction Questionnaires

The Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) measures job satisfaction in 20 facets and has a long form with 100 questions (five items from each facet) and a short form with 20 questions (one item from each facet). Subjects who responded to the "Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire" were asked to indicate their level of satisfaction using a five-point scale for each of the 100 items. The Minnesota Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) has been developed by David J. Weiss, Rene Y Dawis, George W England and Lloyd H Lofquist (1967). The MSQ consists of 100 items. Each item refers to reinforce in the work environment. The respondent indicates how she/he is satisfied with the present job. Five response alternatives will be given. The items appear in blocks of 20 item intervals. Following is the list of MSQ scales. All 100 responses from 20 sub headings will be clubbed to obtain overall job satisfaction score.

1. Ability Utilizations
2. Achievement
3. Activity
4. Advancement
5. Authority
6. College policies and practices
7. Salary
8. Co-faculty members
9. Creativity
10. Independence
11. Moral Values
12. Recognition
13. Responsibilities
14. Security of Job
15. Social Status
16. Social Services
17. HOD's Supervision
18. Management Supervision on working conditions

- 19. Supervision on technical aspects, infrastructure
- 20. General satisfaction

5 Results And Discussion

5.1 Reliability

In order to identify the reliability of the study instrument, Cronbach alpha coefficients were computed. The items had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.931, indicating acceptable reliability. Table 1 presents the results of the reliability analysis.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.931	100

5.2 Chi-Square Test of Independence between gender and satisfaction of respondents

The results of the Chi-Square test for gender and satisfaction were not significant, $\chi^2(2) = 1.58, p = .453$, suggesting that gender and satisfaction could be independent of one another. This implies that the observed frequencies were not significantly different than the expected frequencies. Table 2 presents the results of the Chi-Square test.

Table 2

Observed and Expected Frequencies

Gender	Satisfaction		
	Excellent and good	Poor	Satisfactory
Female	124[128.74]	46[40.61]	46[46.66]
Male	174[169.26]	48[53.39]	62[61.34]

Note. $\chi^2(2) = 1.58, p = .453$. Values formatted as Observed [Expected].

5.3 Chi-Square Test of Independence for Designation and Satisfaction

The results of the Chi-Square test for designation and satisfaction were not significant, $\chi^2(6) = 2.52, p = .866$, suggesting that designation and satisfaction could be independent of one another. This implies that the observed frequencies were not significantly different than the expected frequencies. Table 3 presents the results of the Chi-Square test.

Table 3

Observed and Expected Frequencies

DESIGNATION	Satisfaction		
	Excellent and good	Poor	Satisfactory
Associate Professor	31[29.20]	11[9.21]	7[10.58]
Asst. Professors	254[255.68]	78[80.65]	97[92.66]
HoD	5[4.77]	2[1.50]	1[1.73]
Professor	8[8.34]	3[2.63]	3[3.02]

Note. $\chi^2(6) = 2.52, p = .866$. Values formatted as Observed [Expected].

5.4 Chi-Square Test of Independence for Age and Satisfaction

The results of the Chi-Square test for age and satisfaction were not significant, $\chi^2(10) = 9.99, p = .441$, suggesting that Age and Satisfaction could be independent of one another. This implies that the observed frequencies were not significantly different than the expected frequencies. Table 4 presents the results of the Chi-Square test.

Table 4

Observed and Expected Frequencies

AGEBINNED	Satisfaction		
	Excellent and good	Poor	Satisfactory
30	96[102.51]	40[32.34]	36[37.15]
30 - 34	67[67.35]	18[21.24]	28[24.41]
35 - 40	36[37.55]	10[11.84]	17[13.61]
41 - 45	60[52.45]	11[16.54]	17[19.01]
46 - 51	27[25.63]	9[8.08]	7[9.29]
52+	12[12.52]	6[3.95]	3[4.54]

Note. $\chi^2(10) = 9.99, p = .441$. Values formatted as Observed [Expected].

5.5 Test of ANOVA for significant differences in Age by Satisfaction

The results of the ANOVA were not significant, $F(2, 497) = 0.65, p = .525$, indicating the differences in age among the levels of Satisfaction were all similar (Table 5). The main effect, Satisfaction was not significant at the 95% confidence level, $F(2, 497) = 0.65, p = .525$, indicating there were no significant differences of age by satisfaction levels. The means and standard deviations are presented in Table 5.

Table 5

Analysis of Variance Table for age by Satisfaction

Term	SS	df	F	p	η_p^2
Satisfaction	90.48	2	0.65	.525	0.00
Residuals	34799.00	497			

5.6 Test of ANOVA for significant differences in Experience by Satisfaction

The results of the ANOVA were not significant, $F(2, 497) = 1.57, p = .209$, indicating the differences in experience among the levels of Satisfaction were all similar (Table 6). The main effect, satisfaction was not significant at the 95% confidence level, $F(2, 497) = 1.57, p = .209$, indicating there were no significant differences of Experience by Satisfaction levels. The means and standard deviations are presented in Table 6.

Table 6

Analysis of Variance Table for Experience by Satisfaction

Term	SS	df	F	p	η_p^2
Satisfaction	99.35	2	1.57	.209	0.01
Residuals	15732.22	497			

5.7 Chi-Square Test of Independence for Compensation and satisfaction of employees

A Chi-square Test of Independence was conducted to examine whether compensation and overall satisfaction were independent. The sub items considered for measuring satisfaction towards compensation are: the amount of pay for the work done, the chance to make as

much money as possible (in other sectors), how pay compares with that of similar jobs in other academic institutions, salary and the amount of work done, and whether pay is according to AICTE norms.

Table 7: Chi-square statistics for Compensation & satisfaction of employees

S. No.	Variable	Chi-square statistic	P-value	Result
1	The amount of pay for the work done	13.71	$p = .090$	Not significant
2	The chance to make as much money as possible (In other sectors)	80.62	$p < .001$	Significant
3	How pay compares with that of similar jobs in other academic institutions.	43.15	$p < .001$	Significant
4	Salary and the amount of work done	40.57	$p < .001$	Significant
5	Whether pay is according to AICTE norms	50.24	$p < .001$	Significant

Except for the sub variable amount of pay for the work done and overall satisfaction, The results of the Chi-square test were significant for all other variables ($p < .001$) indicating that the compensation and overall satisfaction are related to one another.

5.8 Chi-Square Test of Independence for working conditions and satisfaction of employees

A Chi-square Test of Independence was conducted to examine whether the working conditions and overall satisfaction were independent. The variables considered include: the working conditions (teaching/research/consultancy), the physical surroundings of the college, the pleasantness of the working conditions, the physical conditions of the job (canteen/Gym/Library/ Lab etc.), the working conditions in the college.

Table 8: Chi-square statistics for working conditions and satisfaction of employees

S.NO	Variable	Chi-square statistic	P-value	Result
1	The working conditions (teaching/research/consultancy)	107.83	$p < .001$	Significant
2	The physical surroundings of the college	110.69	$p < .001$	Significant
3	The pleasantness of the working conditions	129.69	$p < .001$	Significant
4	The physical conditions of the job (canteen/Gym/Library/ Lab etc.)	203.37	$p < .001$	Significant
5	The working conditions in the college	101.14	$p < .001$	Significant

The results of Chi-square test were significant for all sub variables were significant ($p < .001$). Thus, it can be concluded that working conditions and overall satisfaction are related to one another.

6 Conclusions

The data analysis of the present study indicated that gender and job satisfaction were independent of one another. Unlike in some studies cited earlier, satisfaction levels did not differ across gender. Also, the study was suggestive of designation and satisfaction could

be independent of one another. It can be inferred that members were not much considerate about the designations they were holding to be associated with their satisfaction. The study has shown that age of the employees and satisfaction could be independent of one another. The analysis of variance found no significant differences of age by satisfaction levels. Besides, no significant differences were indicated of experience by satisfaction levels. The study has shown that compensation and overall satisfaction are related to one another. Also, the working conditions and overall satisfaction were found to be related to one another.

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